

Bird Species Detection on image using CNN Algorithm

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Abstract: This research paper presents a bird species detection using cascading convolutional network (CNN) method, especially for identifying bird species. The process of identifying birds is complex, and mistakes in the naming of species are common. Therefore, photographs based on a computer system are required to aid bird watchers in the identification process. The proposed work is to explore the feasibility of applying deep learning to the identification of birds by use of a convolutional neural network for feature extraction from photos.

Keywords: Bird species detection , CNN algorithm, Image recognition, Species identification and Bird classification.

I. INTRODUCTION

Bird species identity is crucial for environmental monitoring and conservation initiatives, yet traditional methods often face limitations in accurately and efficiently identifying species. The intricate nature of avian characteristics coupled with human subjectivity poses significant challenges in species identification. However, advancements in deep learning, particularly the use of CNNs, present a promising solution by leveraging visual cues from images to automate the identification process. By harnessing CNNs, researchers can develop robust models capable of recognizing intricate patterns and features unique to different bird species, thereby reducing reliance on manual identification methods prone to errors and biases. This not only streamlines the identification process but also enhances accuracy, enabling more reliable data for biodiversity assessments and conservation planning. Moreover, the integration of CNN-based approaches into conservation efforts can facilitate the monitoring of bird populations in real-time, allowing for timely interventions to mitigate threats and protect vulnerable species. Additionally, the scalability of CNN-based methods enables broader application across diverse ecosystems and geographical regions, providing invaluable insights into the distribution and abundance of bird species worldwide. Overall, the adoption of CNNs for bird species identification represents a significant advancement in conservation science, offering new opportunities to enhance our understanding of avian biodiversity and inform evidence-based

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conservation strategies for safeguarding these vital components of ecosystems

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The literature survey encompasses a multidisciplinary exploration into bird species identification and conservation efforts. Dharaniya et.al [1] delve into bird species identification through Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), emphasizing deep learning's efficacy in classifying species from photo datasets.[2] contribute by exploring automatic bird species recognition from sound spectrograms, showcasing the importance of diverse data modalities in this field. Kumar et al.[3] further extend this research by investigating bird species classification from images, likely discussing various deep learning architectures such as ResNet and VGG16. Meanwhile, Youth et.al [4] provides context on the decline in bird populations over time, underlining the urgency of conservation efforts. This context reinforces the necessity for accurate and efficient species identification techniques, as discussed by Huang and Basanta et.al [5], who offer insights into bird image retrieval and recognition using deep learning techniques, potentially employing CNNs for efficient species identification from image datasets. Collectively, these studies underscore the interdisciplinary nature of bird species identification research and highlight the significance of leveraging advanced technologies to address conservation challenges associated with declining bird populations. Furthermore, they emphasize the importance of continuous research and collaboration between different scientific domains to effectively tackle conservation issues and preserve biodiversity.

III. CNN ALGORITHM

The Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) algorithm, also referred to as ConvNet, is a deep learning algorithm designed for reading visible facts inclusive of photographs. It includes more than one layers, inclusive of convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully linked layers. Here's a brief overview of the CNN set of rules:

Convolutional Layer: This layer applies a set of learnable filters (kernels) to the enter picture, every appearing a convolution operation. The convolution operation includes sliding the filter out

over the input photo and computing element-clever multiplications and summations to provide characteristic maps. These characteristic maps capture distinctive styles gift inside the input picture.

Activation Function: After each convolutional operation, an activation function (generally ReLU - Rectified Linear Unit) is applied detail-sensible to introduce non-linearity into the community, allowing it to analyze complex patterns and relationships within the statistics.

Pooling Layer: The pooling layer reduces the dimensionality of the feature maps while maintaining essential facts. Max pooling is a commonly used pooling technique, in which the maximum fee within a sliding window is retained, effectively down sampling the characteristic maps.

Fully Connected Layer: After numerous convolutional and pooling layers, the function maps are flattened into a one-dimensional vector and passed to 1 or greater absolutely related layers. These layers carry out category based at the found out functions, mapping the enter to the output lessons.

Softmax Activation: The very last layer of the CNN typically makes use of the softmax activation function to transform the uncooked output rankings into possibilities, representing the chance of every magnificence. This permits the CNN to output a probability distribution over the lessons.

By stacking multiple convolutional layers and incorporating pooling and fully linked layers, CNNs can robotically examine hierarchical representations of capabilities from uncooked pixel values, making them extraordinarily powerful for duties which include picture category, object detection, and segmentation.

IV. METHODOLOGY

1. Data Collection:

Gather a diverse set of bird photographs from numerous assets, making sure representation throughout exclusive species, viewpoints, and habitats. This dataset will function the muse for education the version.

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2. Data Preprocessing:

Preprocess the images to make sure uniformity and compatibility with the model architecture. This consists of steps which include disposing of duplicates, cropping snap shots to attention on the chicken, resizing them to a steady length, and making use of records augmentation strategies to boom diversity.

3. Model Selection:

Choose the suitable Deep Learning structure for the task of bird species detection. Common choices encompass Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) such as VGG, ResNet, or Inception, that have validated effectiveness in picture classification duties.

4. Model Training:

Train the chosen model the usage of the preprocessed dataset. During education, the model learns to extract relevant functions from the input snap shots and map them to the corresponding bird species labels. This process entails optimizing the version parameters to decrease a designated loss characteristic, usually using backpropagation and gradient descent algorithms.

5. Model Evaluation:

Evaluate the educated version's overall performance the usage of a separate validation dataset. This entails measuring metrics which includes accuracy, precision, keep in mind, and F1-score to evaluate how well the version generalizes to unseen records.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

```
import streamlit as st
from PIL import Image
from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing.image
load_img,img_to_array
import numpy as np
from keras.models import load_model
model = load_model
lab = {0: 'ABBOTTS BABBLER', 1: 'ABBOTTS BOOBY',
2: }
def processed_img(img_path):
    img=load_img(img_path,target_size=(224,224,3))
    img=img_to_array(img)
    img=img/255
    img=np.expand_dims(img,[0])
    answer=model.predict(img)
    y_class = answer.argmax(axis=-1)
    print(y_class)
    y = " ".join(str(x) for x in y_class)
```

```

y = int(y)
res = lab[y]
print(res)
return res

def run():
    # img1 = Image.open("")
    # img1 = img1.resize((350,350))
    # st.image(img1,use_column_width=False)
    st.title("Bird Species Detection")
    # st.markdown("<<h4 style='text-align: left; color:
    #d73b5c;'>* Data is based "270 Bird Species also see 70
    Sports Dataset"</h4>",
    # unsafe_allow_html=True)

img_file = st.file_uploader("Choose an Image of Bird",
type=["jpg", "png"])
if img_file is not None:
    st.image(img_file,use_column_width=False)
    save_image_path = './upload_images/'+img_file.name
    with open(save_image_path, "wb") as f:
        f.write(img_file.getbuffer())

if st.button("Detect"):
    result = processed_img(save_image_path)
    st.success("Detected Bird is: "+result)
    run()
    
```

```

Total params: 27,886,413 (106.38 MB)

Trainable params: 13,171,725 (50.25 MB)

Non-trainable params: 14,714,688 (56.13 MB)
    
```

VI.Result

This seminar presents the experimental findings of the bird species identity system, highlighting the deep gaining knowledge of version's capacity to correctly distinguish among birds and non-birds photographs. Notably, the device issues error warnings when non-chook photographs are uploaded, ensuring records integrity. the model's excessive accuracy throughout 20 bird species, specifically noteworthy when using the CNN version with pass connections. Moreover, the robustness of the version across versions in bird pics, its generalization to new species past the training dataset, and its comparative performance against baseline techniques underscore its effectiveness in bird species identity obligations. Furthermore, discussions on scalability, performance, blunders analysis, and limitations offer a comprehensive understanding of the model's abilities and potential applications in biodiversity conservation and ecological research.

Model: "functional_1"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
input_layer (InputLayer)	(None, 224, 224, 3)	0
block1_conv1 (Conv2D)	(None, 224, 224, 64)	1,792
block1_conv2 (Conv2D)	(None, 224, 224, 64)	36,928
block1_pool (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 112, 112, 64)	0
block2_conv1 (Conv2D)	(None, 112, 112, 128)	73,856
block2_conv2 (Conv2D)	(None, 112, 112, 128)	147,584
block2_pool (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 56, 56, 128)	0
block3_conv1 (Conv2D)	(None, 56, 56, 256)	295,168

Bird Species Detection

Fig:1_bird species detection

Fig:2_bird species detection

Fig:3_detecting the bird

Fig:4_bird species detection result

VII. CONCLUSION

In response to contemporary challenges in chook species identification, this study proposes the usage of a multi-scale Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) combined with records augmentation strategies to improve accuracy degrees to eighty five-ninety five%. The research addresses boundaries in present structures, aiming to decorate classification accuracy, especially for endangered species. By leveraging deep CNNs with pass connections, the proposed framework offers effective class and analysis of visible information. Analysis of the dataset famous disparities in education samples amongst fowl species, impacting model predictions. Achieving a 92% accuracy charge holds sizeable implications for ecological research and conservation efforts, facilitating biodiversity studies, ecological monitoring, conservation strategies, and citizen technology participation, ultimately aiding in maintaining and information the complexities of bird life.

VII. REFERENCES

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